

WATER QUALITY ANALYSIS OF CHAVDAR LAKE, RAIGAD, MAHARASHTRA**Dr. Gangotri S. Nirbhavane**Associate Professor, Environmental Studies Department,
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gangotrienv@gmail.com**ABSTRACT**

Water is present only on planet earth, therefore, needs to be protected. However, in today's time under the name of development, this vital source gets polluted by man-made activities. Chavdar lake from Mahad selected for study purpose. Water sample collected from July 2013 to October 2013. Water samples were collected from selected sampling sites during the study period and analysed for different parameters like Temperature, pH, Electrical Conductivity, Total Hardness and Turbidity. Obtained results were compared with WHO and BIS standards. All parameters were found within the permissible limits given by BIS and WHO shows water has good quality and not affected by manmade activities.

Keywords

Development, parameters, manmade activities, vital

INTRODUCTION

Water is a very important resource, which is used for number of uses, like domestic use, agricultural use, industrial use etc. It is very important for sustenance of life. People's life and livelihoods depend on water. Rapid growth of population, industrialization, high rate of urbanization and expansion of irrigation activities etc. increases groundwater problem all over India.

Man is using natural resources for his benefit and discharging the different types of solid, liquid waste material into the same resources, which day-by-day degrading the quality of these vital resources. Properties of water make it a reliable source throughout the world. Contamination of water is natural, physical and chemical change due to human activity, so that water is not suitable for use; for which it had previously been suitable. Analysis of water quality determines the suitability of water for different purposes.

Chavdar Talao situated in Raigad district, having a historical importance. It is manmade lake. Purpose of this study to analyse the water quality of Chavdar Talao. Water samples were collected from July 2013 to October 2013.

METHODOLOGY

Water samples were collected from the selected area of Chavdar Talao from July 2013 to October 2013. Sample was collected in 2 lit. Capacity of clean polythene bottles. The bottle was rinsed with the water to be taken for analysis. Tightly sealed after collection and labelled in the field area. Collected sample was analysed for following parameters Temperature, pH, Electrical Conductivity, Total Hardness and Turbidity. The temperatures, pH of the water sample was determined on the spot using a Thermometer and Portable pH meter respectively. Conductivity measured by Conductivity meter. Total hardness was measured by EDTA titrimetric method using EBT indicator. Turbidity measured by Turbidometer. (APHA 2005; Trivedi and Goel1986) The quality of water has been assessed by comparing each parameter with the standard desirable limits prescribed by BIS and WHO.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

After analysis obtained results are shown in table no.1 and further it was compared with the BIS and WHO standards from table no.2.

Table No.1 – Water sample collected from July 2013- October 2013

Month	Temperature (°C)	pH	Electrical Conductivity (µS/cm)	Total Hardness (mg/l)	Turbidity (NTU)
July.2013	23	6.8	180.4	226	1.2
Aug.2013	22	7.2	192.6	252	1
Sep.2013	21	7.6	220.6	288	0.8
Oct.2013	24	7.4	218.2	298	0.6

Table No.2: Drinking water standards

Sr. No.	Parameters	BIS (IS 10500-91)			WHO
		Desirable Limit	Max. permissible Limits in the absence of alternate source		
1	Temperature (°C)	-	-	-	-
2	pH	6.5 to8.5	No relaxation		6.5 – 8.5
3	Electrical Conductivity (µS/cm)	-	300		-
4	Total hardness as CaCO ₃ (mg/l)	200	600		500
5	Turbidity (NTU)	-	5		5

Temperature-Temperature ranges from 21°C to 24°C during study period. Highest temperature was observed in October 2013. Higher value of temperature has accelerated the rate of chemical reactions in the water (Kataria, 2009).

pH- pH ranges from 6.8 to 7.6 during study period. All the samples were found within the desirable limit given by BIS and WHO. In the month of September 2013 highest pH was observed. pH is a significant parameter in water body as most of the aquatic organisms are adapted to an average pH and do not survive in sudden changes. pH of water is influenced by geology of catchments area and buffering capacity of water (Shyamala *et.al.*,2008).

Conductance-Conductance was ranged from 180.4 to 220.6 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$ during study period. Highest conductance was observed in the month of September 2013 i.e.220.6. All samples were found within the permissible limits given by BIS. Electrical conductance increases with salts present in it, higher the electrolyte concentration in water, the more is its electrical conductance. Conductivity is proportional to the dissolved solids. Both showed analogous trend in seasonal variation (Gupta *et.al.*, 2009).

Total Hardness- Total hardness ranges from 226 to 298 mg/l during study period. Highest hardness observed in the month of October 2013. During study period all samples were found above the desirable limit given by BIS, i.e.200mg/l, but all the samples were found within the permissible limit given by BIS and WHO i.e.600 and 500 respectively. The high concentration of Total Hardness in water Samples may be due to dissolution of polyvalent metallic ions from sedimentary rocks, seepage and run off from the soil (Gupta *et.al.*, 2009).

Turbidity- Turbidity in study area ranges from 0.6 to 1.2 NTU during study period. Highest turbidity observed in the month of July 2013 and lowest turbidity observed in the month of September 2013. Turbidity is a key parameter for characterizing the quality of water. Turbidity in water may be due to large variety of suspended materials, which range in size from colloidal to coarse dispersions, depending upon the degree of turbulence (Prakash and Somshekar, 2006).

CONCLUSION

Water samples collected from Chavdar lake was found within the permissible limit given by BIS and WHO for pH, Electrical Conductivity, Turbidity parameters. Total Hardness in water body was observed above desirable limit given by BIS, but it is within permissible limits given by BIS and WHO. Chavdar lake has good water quality, which is well maintained by Municipal Corporation of Mahad. Less interference of people into waterbody, regular check-up for water quality, cleanliness around lake helps to maintain water quality.

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